

MECHANISMS OF FUNCTIONING OF LOGISTIC STRUCTURES

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Abstract. *This article discusses the use of various technologies for warehouse processing of goods, modern technical means, equipment, a complex of warehouses, sites for storing containers, handling mechanisms, vehicles, weight facilities and a number of other technical means that ensure the acceptance, processing and dispatch of various products. according to shipping documents.*

Keywords: *logistics, mechanism, complex, processing, cargo, transport, equipment.*

Introduction. Modern logistical mechanisms of supply chain management affect problems of various nature. First of all, this is the part of the tasks that relates to the field of marketing, since exchange is carried out on the basis of strategies, and then physical distribution.

Materials management performs the functions of the movement of the commodity flow until the moment the goods leave the supply chain.

Logistic chain - a set of links of the logistics system, linearly ordered, optimized for material, information, financial flow in order to design a certain set of logistics functions or costs

It is appropriate to note that the logistics approach in solving the problems of improving supply chain management goes beyond such logistics functions that are associated with the formation of economic relations and the conduct of contractual campaigns, the coordination of various options for the supply basis, based on the choice of rational forms of transportation of goods by consumers.

The supply chain consists of a number of functional elements, such as the production of goods, distribution and transportation channels, the organization of sales of goods, their promotion to markets using various communication strategies. Moreover, the choice of the type of strategies depends on the segmentation of consumers and product positioning.

Dispatching and control are also an integral part of logistics technologies for managing commodity flows. But, along with these elements, there are a number of other functional links in the supply chain, with the help of which a set of tasks is solved to support the rhythm and timeliness of the delivery of goods at the right time and place according to consumer orders.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract mantic thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. Thus, the logistics of supply is connected with the cycle of work that is carried out as part of the marketing strategy. This relationship not only follows from the very essence of the supply chain process, but is also a necessary condition for the effective operation of sellers in the market.

Of course, representing a multi-level logistics system, the supply chain is associated with the physical distribution of goods, their promotion to the consumer. At this stage, the management of material resources is to exclude the transportation of goods as much as possible and reduce transportation and procurement costs.

The concept of the supply chain can be represented as follows. Study objectives:

- to study marketing channels and their functions;
- understand the role of influencers in the marketing channel;
- learn the essence and meaning of the sorting function;
- to know the role of the mediator of the channel;
- understand the essence and functioning of the supply chain and the differences from the marketing channel;
- get acquainted with the essence of partnership in the field of logistics.

These are the main tasks to be solved when analyzing the effectiveness of supply chain management.

Although great importance is attached to the integration of participants in the logistics chain, which includes various intermediaries (distributors, dealers, franchisors, etc.), as well as business-supporting organizations.

Considering the components of the conceptual apparatus of logistics, one should pay attention to procurement logistics, which is a complex of various functions performed in the process of organizing future deliveries of goods according to consumer orders. Its essence is reflected in the fact that before the consumer receives the necessary goods, he must choose a supplier, determine the form of delivery and other parameters: shipment volumes, delivery times, and then conclude a contract (agreement), which will clearly regulate the contractual obligations of the parties.

Purchasing logistics aims to activate the work of manufacturers in the market.

In procurement logistics, a large role belongs to dealing services, with the help of which a package of commercial documents is prepared that mediates the organization of the supply of goods.

The formation of the structure of purchases of goods affects the issues of financial management, since the resources necessary for this must be accumulated to pay the bills of suppliers. Moreover, the forms and methods of payment are selected taking into account the requirements of counterparties and contractual conditions.

To study the features of the logistics model of supply chain management, it is very important to distinguish between features between logistics and marketing channels.

Marketing channels are a set of processes that provide exchange procedures and are performed by a coordinated group of firms.

It should be understood from the outset that marketing channels are not just about satisfying demand by delivering goods (or services) of the right quality, in the right quantity, to the right place, and at the right price.

They also serve to generate demand through the promotional activities of each participant (i.e., firms, manufacturers, wholesalers, distribution centers, and retailers) that make up these channels.

Therefore, the channel should be considered as an organized network that presents the product to the consumer, subject to the achievement of an optimal combination of factors such as time, place, price and quality.

The logistics channel always deals with the physical movement of the product.

One of the main functions of the logistics channel, which significantly affects the operation of other channels, is the sorting function. The sorting function is divided into four stages. Sorting is the redistribution of goods into homogeneous sets.

Accumulation – this collection of homogeneous products from various sources.

Distribution is the division of batches of homogeneous goods into smaller batches.

Picking is the creation of sets of dissimilar products of goods for resale, usually to a retailer.

Channel intermediaries. For example, in a negotiation channel, a broker is contacted. A broker is an intermediary between a seller and a buyer. When chartering a vessel, brokers perform the functions of the hirer, and on the other hand, the owner of the vessel.

Intermediaries in the financing channel are banks that provide a loan for a transaction.

Intermediaries in the promotion channel are advertising companies.

The most common intermediary in the logistics channel are forwarding agencies.

Logistics principle organizations wholesale trade provide creation region a three-level commodity distribution systems, basic task which is rational bringing to consumers of various types of products with minimal total costs, performing a set of functions for managing commodity and information flows.

But before how product will sold, it passes some hierarchical steps in the process of moving to the consumer.

Key aspect of logistics - physical distribution, covering a wide range of activities designed to efficiently move finished goods out of the production line. Physical distribution is wider than transportation, and includes such important areas that require independent decisions such as: control, inventory, handling, protective packaging, order processing, transportation, warehousing and warehousing.

The regulatory mechanism that allows scheduling this process is the logistics center with the appropriate infrastructure. The shorter the route of movement of goods in the circulation channel, the more efficient, the higher the level of profitability of sales and the profitability of marketing activities.

In contrast to the previously existing stock supply system, the logistics model for managing commodity flows is based on modern technological solutions in the field of cargo movement, warehousing, storage and preparation of products for sale using bar-coding systems and monitoring the intensity of sales of goods that have entered the logistics network, taking into account consumer demand.

Logistics technologies for managing the movement of goods provide for the availability of commodity distribution centers, warehouse terminals capable of processing large batches of goods for various purposes and for a wide range of consumers.

For these purposes, package-forming technologies, modern storage equipment (pallets, gravity and mobile racks), container transportation of goods, route delivery of goods to intermediate warehouses - distributors are used.

The central link of the logistics process can be represented by a large warehouse terminal with a control superstructure that has information and computing system that keeps records and controls the movement of goods from the moment it enters the distribution network to the stage of direct sales by the end user.

Information support of the logistics system is carried out with the help of a powerful computer center and communication networks.

Suffice it to say that it is common for a modern logistics center to process data with a branched structure of information arrays and for a set of tasks included in the subsystems for automated management of warehouse operations and financial and accounting calculations, etc.

Depending on the type of product, a variety of warehouse processing technologies and modern technical means and equipment are used. Warehouse terminals operating as part of logistics centers are a complex of warehouses, sites for storing containers, loading and unloading mechanisms, vehicles, weighing facilities and a number of other technical means that ensure the acceptance, processing and dispatch of various products according to shipping documents. Motion of commodity flows within the warehouse terminal allows not only to solve the problem of disassembling incoming batches of products according to consumer orders, but also to minimize the costs of storage and processing of products, and to eliminate irrational transshipments in the future. Moreover, the main task of the logistics link is not the organization of sales of goods, since trade operations are carried out in the trading link. They provide services for the organization of product distribution from the manufacturer to the consumer. Logistics centers are becoming the main link in the logistics chain, ensuring the effective functioning of wholesale markets, where goods are sold to customers.

Performing the functions of the process of scheduling the distribution of goods, the logistics center interacts with the commercial link of the wholesale markets, executing consumer orders in a timely and high-quality manner.

From the above analysis of the state of development of the distribution network, we can conclude that territorial warehouses - distributors play an important role in maintaining a stable level of commodity stocks and promptly solving the problems of smoothing the emerging shortages in certain types of goods. Logistics service systems for market entities allow the latter to focus on the commercial aspect, that is, on solving the problems of expanding the scope of business in the wholesale trade.

Let us consider the technological sequence of work on servicing commodity flows received from consignors of goods (manufacturers, industrial firms, etc.). It is represented by a combination of various procedures and operations for customs clearance, warehousing and disaggregation of consignments of goods, the formation of product packages in the directions of shipment and the rationalization of intra-regional transportation.

The main commodity distribution center performs the functions of consolidating the flow of goods coming through the existing transport transnational corridors for technological processing (unloading, sorting, warehousing, packaging and preparing consignments of goods for shipment, etc.). Moreover, its main role is to promote disaggregated consignments of goods along the logistics chain to the territorial distribution centers of that part of the cargo units that are intended for smaller consumers.

The physical distribution of products is accompanied by operations for its insurance, financing and preparation for production consumption, and at each stage of the movement of products, various service structures are connected to the logistics process, especially when selling equipment and technical means that require after-sales service, as well as other infrastructure links serving market entities.

An important link in the logistics system is forwarding services that provide delivery and forwarding of goods.

The creation of logistics structures is preceded by the stage of internal restructuring of the distribution network, improvement of organizational management systems due to the differentiation of their functions.

A characteristic feature of commodity circulation is the multi-channel factor, the presence of a large number of commercial structures that import products in small batches.

Such a technology for the physical distribution of products contradicts the mechanism of functioning of the logistics model, acting as a separate type of supply systems and operating in parallel with logistics-type structures, generating multiple transshipments and an increase in the cost of goods.

To solve the problems of complex provision of material resources, for example, capital construction, large-scale industrial production and other areas of material production, these distribution channels are ineffective.

The links of the logistics system should include product sales centers. It is necessary to consider in more detail their purpose as a commercial link that completes the process of logistical promotion of goods. The more diverse the forms of organization of sales (transit, wholesale, small wholesale, etc.), the more perfect the mechanism for the functioning of wholesale markets. On a certain scale, a form of marketing, commercial franchising is productive.

The development of logistics systems contributes to a comprehensive solution of the problems of increasing the efficiency of servicing market entities, responding to their demand.

Based on the conceptual provisions regarding the strategies for the development of market infrastructure, their logistics component plays one of the main roles in achieving harmonization of the process of free purchase and sale of goods. Therefore, a characteristic feature of the ongoing transformations in the market of means of production is that the links of the logistics system not only ensure the implementation of the main technological operations to bring products to consumers using various modes of transportation, but also create an integral system of division of labor in the sphere of circulation.

Summary

In this regard, it is appropriate to pay attention to the fact that the existing distribution channels are disintegrated, the system of cooperation between them is poorly developed, the existing storage facilities without logistical support are used inefficiently, and the active part of the production assets of the wholesale link does not meet the requirements of scientific and technological progress.

Despite the high density of incoming commodity flows and adequate volumes of information on their management, most of

Warehouse space does not have automated systems for managing warehouse operations. The share of manual labor in loading and unloading operations, during the transportation of products is high.

The state of development of the elements of the third level logistics chain shows that there are specialized divisions in the commercial link that ensure the promotion of services and finished products that have passed the stage of industrial processing.

The modernization of existing transport and storage systems requires large capital investments (investments), therefore, a very effective direction is the investment design of

logistics centers with the participation of foreign investors focused on the long term, able to consolidate incoming flows and organize their physical distribution in an optimal way.

Naturally, the creation of logistics systems will require a certain restructuring of the functioning channels of logistics and sales, especially industry segments of the market.

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